

**Toward a revised checklist of the Western Palearctic butterflies, hyperlinked to the original descriptions at species, genus and family level (Lepidoptera, Papilionoidea)
Part III: Rationale and framework for the Pieridae.**

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Abstract

Taxonomic and nomenclatural issues concerning the butterfly family Pieridae are reviewed in light of the rules of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN), historical classifications, recent phylogenetic studies and current usage. Particular attention is given to the classification of subfamilies and tribes, where older names and synonymies have sometimes conflicted with prevailing usage, requiring rigorous evaluation under the Code.

At the tribal level, the status of Aporiini is discussed. The various interpretations concerning the species composition of certain genera are examined, and the decisions adopted for the compilation of the checklist are explained, particularly for the genera *Leptidea*, *Gonepteryx* and *Colias*. The status of the genus *Belenois* and its placement within the classification, including the resulting modifications to the checklist, are clarified. Finally, the generic structure within the tribe Anthocharidini is analysed.

Key words

Taxonomy — Checklist — Papilionoidea — Pieridae — Dismorphiinae — Coliadinae — Pierinae — Aporiini — Anthocharidini — *Leptidea* — *Leptidea morsei* — *Gonepteryx* — *Colias* — *Belenois* — *Euchloe* — *Iberochloe* — *Elphinstonia* — *Anthocharis* — *Euchloe pechi* — *Zegris meridionalis* — Western Palearctic.

Introduction

Nomenclatural stability within Pieridae requires consistent application of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature combined with careful consideration of historical usage and current taxonomic practice. Despite extensive study, the family remains affected by long-standing issues arising from historical name proliferation, changing generic and subfamilial concepts, and differing regional interpretations. Recent molecular studies have clarified several relationships but have also produced conflicting or incomplete results, particularly where taxon sampling is limited. The present revised checklist of Western Palearctic Pieridae Nomenclatural stability within Pieridae requires consistent application of the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature combined with careful consideration of historical usage and current taxonomic practice. Despite extensive study, the family remains affected by long-standing issues arising from historical name proliferation, changing generic and subfamilial concepts, and differing regional interpretations. Recent molecular studies have clarified several relationships but have also produced conflicting or incomplete results, particularly where taxon sampling is limited. The present revised checklist of West Palearctic Pieridae therefore follows a pragmatic approach, retaining well-established names where justified, applying ICZN provisions consistently, and documenting the rationale for each taxonomic decision. Unresolved cases are explicitly identified, providing a transparent and stable reference framework while indicating areas where further integrative research is required.

1. Classification of Tribes in the Subfamily Pierinae

1.1. Introduction

The group-family level classification adopted in the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), encompassing superfamilies, families, subfamilies, tribes and subtribes, largely follows the most recent phylogenetic studies on Pieridae (Braby *et al.* 2006; Wahlberg *et al.* 2014; Ding & Zhang 2016; Wei *et al.*, 2022; Kawahara *et al.*, 2023; Carvalho *et al.* 2024), with the notable exception of the Aporiini. The rationale for this exception and the approach adopted are discussed below.

1.2. Context

Unfortunately, the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature (ICZN) provides no biological, morphological, phylogenetic or genetic criteria for the recognition of taxa at the group-family level. The Code regulates nomenclature rather than taxa themselves and therefore does not define what constitutes a family or how it should be delineated.

Prior to phylogenetic analyses, group-family ranks were assigned at the discretion of individual systematists, based on a variety of criteria. These could include the structure of the exoskeleton, wing venation, legs, palpi, genitalia or life-history traits such as eggs, larvae and pupae. By considering these characteristics, systematists aimed to provide a conceptual framework for grouping species progressively into increasingly smaller sets, ultimately resulting in genus-level classifications that comprised only a few species.

In contrast, contemporary phylogenetic studies adopt a more objective approach by linking taxonomic ranks to the historical timing of lineage divergences. For instance, in Kawahara *et al.* (2023), the temporal intervals used to define classification levels are: families between 100 and 80 Ma, subfamilies between 80 and 60 Ma, tribes between 60 and 40 Ma, and subtribes between 40 and 20 Ma. This method is therefore anchored in estimated divergence times derived from mathematical models and can be considered less subjectively influenced. These intervals do not necessarily correspond to geological epochs (e.g., the 60 to 40 Ma interval used to define tribes spans the mid-Palaeocene to mid-Eocene). Nevertheless, the advantage of this approach is that it bases classification on a consistent, objective criterion, whereas its drawback is the exclusion of other potentially informative characteristics.

1.3. Conclusion

Regarding the Aporiini/Aporiina, Kawahara *et al.* (2023) recognise the group's monophyly but include it within the Pierini. Their supplementary phylogenetic tree indicates that the Aporiini/Aporiina branch diverged from the Pierini at an estimated 36 Ma. Thus, based on an estimated 4 Ma divergence interval (subjectively calculated), the Aporiini/Aporiina are treated as a subtribe.

The last author to consider Aporiini/Aporiina at the tribe level was Braby (2005) in his *Provisional Checklist of Genera of the Pieridae*. What is the rationale for following this relatively older study rather than more recent ones? First, from a technical perspective, available evidence strongly supports the monophyly of the group. Second, although it is represented by a single species in the European fauna, the group is widely distributed globally, encompassing over 400 species. Recognizing it as a tribe allows for further subdivision into subtribes; for example, *Belenois* (and closely related genera) could constitute a distinct subtribe, separate from *Delias* (and related genera) or other genus-level clusters.

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2. Classification within the Genus *Leptidea* Billberg, 1820

2.1. Reference classification

Since the discovery of a new species within the genus *Leptidea* by Real (1988), researchers (Lorković 1993; Mazel 2000–2002; ...) have examined this genus in detail, first using classical methods (such as genitalia) and later based on DNA or karyological data, which led to the discovery of a second new, cryptic species (Dincă *et al.* 2011).

Entomologists are therefore confronted with newly recognised species that cannot be reliably identified in the field by their habitus. *Leptidea reali* Reissinger, [1990] and *Leptidea juvernica* Williams, 1946 can be distinguished from *Leptidea sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758) by their genitalia (male or female), but *L. reali* and *L. juvernica* can only be reliably separated by barcoding.

The names assigned to these recently described species may still change, as they were previously confused with *L. sinapis*, a species to which numerous infraspecific taxa had been attributed.

2.2. What is the original status, authorship and date of *L. morsei*?

Two publications from 1882 compete for priority:

a) *Leucophasia morsei* Fenton, 1882. In: Ishikawa, *Papilio* 2(3): 35–36, fig 3-4. The publication date printed in the journal is March 1882.

b) *Leptosia morsei* Fenton, [1882]. In: Butler, *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London* 1881: 855. The publication date printed in the journal is 15 November 1881, but the actual distribution date was very likely in 1882.

There is therefore considerable uncertainty regarding the actual distribution dates of these works. The approach adopted here is to follow Bozano *et al.* (2016), the most recent monograph treating the Dismorphiinae of the Palearctic fauna.

2.3. Conclusion

In the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), *L. sinapis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *L. reali* Reissinger, [1990], *L. juvernica* Williams, 1946, *L. duponcheli* (Staudinger, 1871) and *L. morsei* (Fenton, 1882) are adopted.

2.4. References

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3. Classification within the Genus *Gonepteryx* Leach, 1815

3.1. Introduction

The various species of this genus are relatively well known. Nevertheless, the specific status of the taxa from the Canary Islands remains uncertain, as the conclusions of several recent studies are somewhat divergent. The phylogenetic study of the genus by Brunton *et al.* (1998) concluded that three putative species occur in the Canary Islands: *Gonepteryx cleobule* (Hübner, [1824]), *G. eversi* Rehnelt, 1974 and *G. palmae* Stamm, 1963. Although Dapporto *et al.* (2022) recognise only a single species on these islands, *G. cleobule*, the figure depicting the haplotype network nonetheless reveals a significant separation among the three taxa proposed by Brunton *et al.* (1998). However, the barcoding data show a maximum p-distance of only 2.1% (corresponding to 11 mutations in the mitochondrial COI gene), based on a limited sample of 13 specimens from three islands. As no nuclear data are available, these results should be interpreted with caution.

In his monograph on the genus, Bozano *et al.* (2016) retain only two species for the Canary Islands, *G. cleobule* and *G. palmae*, and treat *G. eversi* as a subspecies of *G. cleobule*. Plates of male genitalia (by Coutsis J.) demonstrate that there is a significant difference in the structure of the male genitalia between *G. cleobule* and *G. palmae*. Are these differences sufficient to ensure reproductive isolation of these insular populations?

3.2. Conclusion

In the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), *G. cleobule* and *G. palmae* are adopted for the *Gonepteryx* of the Canary Islands.

3.3. References

Bozano G., Coutsis J., Herman P., Allegrucci G., Cesaroni D. & Sbordoni V. 2016. *Guide to the Butterflies of the Palearctic Region*. Pieridae part 3, Subfamily Coliadinae (tribes Rhodocerini, Euremini and Catopsilia), Subfamily Dismorphiinae. — Milano: Omnes Artes (Ed.). 70 p.

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4. Classification within the Genus *Colias* Fabricius, 1807

4.1. Introduction

Colias represents a species-rich genus with a broad global distribution, but its internal classification has long been debated.

Early work by Berger (1986) examined the genus in detail and proposed a subdivision into several subgenera based primarily on the morphology of tergite 8.

Verhulst's extensive monograph (2000) took a complementary approach, relying predominantly on habitus and biological traits for species delimitation. While thorough in descriptive scope, this latter work did not incorporate a broader set of morphological or molecular characters, which may limit its ability to unravel evolutionary relationships and refine the systematics of the genus.

Significant nomenclatural efforts have since aimed to clarify the taxonomic foundation of the genus.

Grieshuber & Lamas (2007) compiled a synonymic list intended to provide a complete and authoritative account of all available names in *Colias*, acknowledging that many taxa remain provisionally interpreted in the absence of comprehensive evidence, and underscoring the difficulty of deciding whether phenotypically distinct populations represent full species or geographic races.

The annotated catalogue by Grieshuber, Worthy & Lamas (2012) further extended these efforts by examining type material from major museum collections and providing detailed taxonomic status for Old World taxa.

Prior to the advent of modern phylogenetic studies, few systematic treatments used criteria beyond morphology or ecology to differentiate species or subgenera.

Early phylogenetic work, often based on a restricted sampling of taxa and loci, produced results that were at times contradictory or unexpected with respect to subgroup delineation and evolutionary relationships.

This has highlighted the need for broader taxon sampling and multiple lines of evidence.

Only recently has a comprehensive phylogenetic study addressed this need: Mo *et al.* (2024) analysed a large dataset to assign confirmed species to well-supported clades and to investigate diversification across the genus.

The clades identified in this study correspond only partially to the subgenera proposed by Berger (1986), indicating that traditional morphological classifications, while informative, do not always fully reflect evolutionary relationships.

4.2. Conclusion

The subdivision of *Colias* into subgenera will require a full systematic revision of the genus. The checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), will need to be updated regarding species arrangement on the basis of the results presented by Mo *et al.* (2024).

4.3. References

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5. Classification of the *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758) complex

5.1. Introduction

The *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758) complex comprises several taxa for which species status remains to be demonstrated. A comprehensive monograph covering all potential species (Eitschberger 1983) recognised the following species for the western Palaearctic region: *Pieris napi* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pieris bryoniae* (Hübner, [1806]), *Pieris pseudorapae* Verity, 1908 which consists of three subspecies, *pseudorapae* Verity from Lebanon, *suffusa* Sheljuzhko, 1931 from southern Russia, and *balcana* Lorkovic, 1968 from the Balkans, and *Pieris segonzaci* Le Cerf, 1923. This study relied on a broad set of criteria, including ecology, habitus, the morphology of legs and androconia, male genitalia, eggs, and other characters, to establish the species listed above. Reissinger (1990), in his checklist, adopted Eitschberger's classification unchanged.

However, the results of hybridisation experiments (Lorkovic 1970; Hesselbarth *et al.* 1995) challenge this classification, as they showed that the Asia Minor and Caucasian taxa previously assigned to *P. pseudorapae* can freely hybridise with *P. napi*, whereas *balcana* cannot.

Dapporto *et al.* (2022), in *The Atlas of Mitochondrial Genetic Diversity for Western Palearctic Butterflies*, recognised the following species: *P. balcana*, *P. bryoniae*, *P. napi*, and *P. segonzaci*.

However, a recent genomic study posted as a bioRxiv preprint (Sala-Garcia *et al.* 2025) using broad phylogenomic and population genomic data across the *Pieris napi* group suggests patterns of phylogenetic relationships, population structure and ecological differentiation that may not fully align with purely mitochondrial or morphology-based taxonomies, and it highlights the need for further evaluation once the work has undergone formal peer review.

5.2. Conclusion

The checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), is aligned with the taxonomic conclusions of the most recent peer-reviewed study.

5.3. References

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6. The position of the Genus *Belenois* Hübner, [1819] in the classification

6.1. Introduction

The study by Kawahara A. *et al.* (2023) provides evidence that the genus *Belenois* is a member of the subtribe Aporiina. As noted in point 1 above, the status of this subtribe has been revised, and it is now recognised as the tribe Aporiini.

6.2. Conclusion

The genus *Belenois* Hübner, [1819], together with its subgenus *Anaphaeis* Hübner, [1819], and its sole species recorded in the western Palaeartic, *Belenois aurota* (Fabricius, 1793), should consequently be positioned in the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), immediately after *Aporia crataegi* (Linnaeus, 1758).

6.3. References

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7. Structure of the genera within the tribe Anthocharidini Scudder, 1889

7.1. Introduction

The tribe Anthocharodini constitutes a well-supported monophyletic clade, clearly distinct from the Pierini (Kawahara A.Y. *et al.* 2023). Nonetheless, the internal generic structure of this tribe has been the focus of several competing and markedly divergent hypotheses. Tracing back to Higgins (1975), the classification of genera, based primarily on male genitalia morphology, was as follows: *Euchloe* Hübner, [1819] (including *tagis* (Hübner, [1804])), *Elphinstonia* Klots, 1930, *Anthocharis* Boisduval, Rambur & Graslín, [1833], and *Zegrís* Boisduval, 1836. Between 1979 and 2013, Back conducted extensive studies on the biology of numerous species within this group and published multiple papers reporting his findings, without revising the generic framework. The studies by Back, Knebelberger and Miller (2006, 2008), however, fundamentally reshaped the overall framework of this group. First, the genus *Iberochloe* Back, Knebelberger and Miller, 2008, was established to accommodate two species, *tagis* Hübner, [1804], and *pechi* Staudinger, 1885. For clarity, a concise summary of the various proposed generic arrangements within the tribe is presented below:

Back, Knebelberger & Miller (2008): *Euchloe* + ((*Iberochloe* + *Anthocharis*) + *Elphinstonia*)

Back, Miller & Opler (2011): *Euchloe* + ((*Iberochloe* + *Elphinstonia*) + *Anthocharis*)

Back (2020: 10): (*Euchloe* + (*Zegris* + *Elphinstonia*)) + (*Anthocharis* + *Iberochloe*)

Kawahara A. *et al.* (2023): (*Anthocharis* + *Euchloe*) + *Zegris*

In view of these alternative hypotheses, Marabuto *et al.* (2020) recommended, as a taxonomic outcome of their study, retaining *Euchloe*, *Elphinstonia* and *Iberochloe* as subgenera of *Euchloe*. Dapporto *et al.* (2022) recognise only three genera, listed alphabetically as *Anthocharis*, *Euchloe* and *Zegris*, and treat the species assigned by Back (2020) and Marabuto *et al.* (2020), both at subgeneric level, to *Iberochloe* and *Elphinstonia* as members of *Euchloe*.

7.2. Conclusion

Views on the delimitation and hierarchical rank of genera within the tribe remain diverse and, in several cases, mutually contradictory. In the face of this ongoing instability, the checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), follows the generic and specific framework adopted by Dapporto *et al.* (2022), with two exceptions. The checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), includes *Euchloe pechi* (Staudinger, 1885), as the genetic divergence reported in that study is relatively substantial and its habitus is highly distinctive. However, this placement remains provisional, as Back (1984) demonstrated that Algerian and European populations exhibit an exceptionally high degree of reproductive compatibility, with natural copulation occurring readily and no developmental anomalies or particular susceptibilities observed in the offspring.

Back (2020) treated *Zegris meridionalis* (Lederer, 1853) as a valid species. In line with Dapporto *et al.* (2022), the present checklist (Taymans & Cuvelier 2025), considers *meridionalis* to be a subspecies of *Zegris eupheme* (Esper, [1804]).

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Sylvain Cuvelier: analysis, validation, visualisation, writing – review and editing.

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